

IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPREHENSIVE WATER, SANITATION AND HYGIENE PROGRAM IN SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN DIVISION OF LAGUNA

Danica B. Tarsona

*Quinale Elementary School, Paete, Laguna, Philippines
Laguna State Polytechnic University, Siniloan, Laguna, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study determined the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WinS) Program in selected public elementary schools in the Schools Division Office of Laguna. It also evaluated its relationship to pupils' healthy lifestyle, attitudes, norms, behaviors, and academic performance. A descriptive-evaluative survey questionnaire was distributed to school heads, health coordinators, and learners to gather data. A two set of questionnaires were administered and retrieved from eight (8) schools located in the municipalities of Siniloan, Santa Maria, Pakil, Paete, Mabitac, Lumban, Kalayaan, and Pagsanjan involving 8 school health coordinators, 170 teacher-respondents, and 367 pupils. The responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated according to weighted mean and rank, and Spearman Correlation was used to test its significant relationship. The study revealed that the implementation of the WASH program was at a high extent across all components, with schools ensuring access to safe drinking water, maintaining clean sanitation facilities, conducting supervised handwashing and toothbrushing, and integrating hygiene education into classroom activities. Learners showed positive attitudes and maintained consistent hygiene practices, which contributed to participation and lowered illness-related absences. Statistical analysis revealed significant relationships between WinS implementation, students' health behaviors, and academic achievement, indicating that better sanitation and hygiene directly enhanced learning outcomes. The study also identified unique practices such as student-driven hygiene campaigns, buddy systems for hygiene support, eco-incentive waste initiatives, and active participation from stakeholders, all of which reinforced program delivery. Overall, the findings concluded that effective implementation of the comprehensive WinS program creates a secure and nurturing learning environment while improving students' health and academic achievement. The findings emphasized strengthening the WinS program by improving toilet access and expanding WASH

initiatives. Schools should upgrade facilities, teachers and parents should reinforce hygiene practices, and policymakers and stakeholders must support funding and sustainability.

Keywords: *academic achievement ,hygiene, water, sanitation, WinS Program,*

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization emphasizes that accessibility to clean drinking water, sanitation and hygiene education is an integral part of the WASH in Schools program, which is closely linked to Sustainable Development Goals 3, 4, and 6.

Inadequate provision of WASH facilities can lead to the transmission of diseases such as diarrhea and hepatitis A, negatively affecting school attendance, academic performance, and the overall well-being of learners, particularly in resource-poor communities. (WHO 2025).

Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) are human rights linked to fundamental needs, and therefore, influence the survival and satisfaction of higher needs (Chirgwin et al., 2021). From this perspective, governments are initially interested in achieving universal WASH coverage.

In addition to WASH facilities, the WHO (2025) further emphasizes that WASH in Schools also includes behavioral change and hygiene education, such as hand washing with soap, appropriate sanitation, and proper handling of menstruation. However, billions of people worldwide do not have direct access to these fundamental sanitary services; as the WHO and UNICEF Joint Monitoring Program (JMP) documented 2 billion people without safe water supply and 4.5 billion who lack safe and well-managed sanitation facilities. In fact, about 1 billion practice open defecation, and most of them are located in South Asia and in Sub-Saharan Africa. The worst rates of accessibility to safe drinking water sources and hygiene facilities were also recorded sub-Saharan Africa. Around 400 million people in the area use surface water, and some need more than 30-minute round trip to access water sources.

Ensuring universal access to water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) is one of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals for 2030. One notable strategy to achieve this is to provide schools with a sustainable, safe water supply points, as well as handwashing and sanitation facilities; however, limited studies have assessed comprehensive school WASH services (UNICEF, 2020). The UN SDGs also recognize the importance of participation and support on enhancing water and sanitation management (Tseklevs, E.et. al., 2022).

According to the World Health Organization, only 14 countries had data on basic hygiene in health care facilities, including at points of care and toilets, and 55 countries

had data on functional hand hygiene facilities with water and soap or alcohol-based rubs supply (WHO, 2020).

Schools play a vital role in children's early life development and in the mitigation and control of disease transmission. Yusuf (2020) stated that both the control and spread of infectious diseases, such as gastrointestinal diseases or respiratory infections, including COVID-19 depend heavily on students' access to and the quality of WASH infrastructure. McMichael (2019), on the other hand, noted that because many students spend significant time in school, these environments are crucial for pupils' physical and cognitive development, as well as their well-being.

Several factors affect the students' performance in school, and one of the most frequently overlooked is the consideration given to meeting children's basic physical needs. These include access to adequate, safe drinking water alongside, clean, accessible, and child-friendly toilets equipped with functional handwashing facilities. The absence or insufficiency of such facilities could result in children's increased susceptibility to illness, which could compromise their learning capacities. According to the study conducted by the United Nations Children's Fund (2020) two out of five people in the world do not have a handwashing facility with soap and water on the premises. This implies that nearly half of the schools globally lack handwashing facilities with soap and water available to students.

Given these concerns, this study focused on the implementation of the Comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Laguna. By assessing current practices and identifying areas for improvement, the research aimed to enhance the effectiveness of the WASH in Schools (WinS) program in promoting a safe, healthy, and supportive learning environment for all learners.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program in public elementary schools, in terms of:
 - 1.1 Water Access;
 - 1.2 Sanitation;
 - 1.3 Hygiene;
 - 1.4 Deworming; and
 - 1.5 Hygiene Education?
2. What is the extent of sanitation of pupils as to healthy lifestyle, preventive health services and responsibility for own health?
3. What is the extent of planned behavior of pupils as to attitude, norms and behavioral intentions?
4. What is the academic performance of pupils in school?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the learners' attitude, norms, and behaviors and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program in public elementary schools?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the Learners' Healthy Lifestyle Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for Own Health and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program in public elementary schools?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of attitude, norms, and behavioral intentions on academic performance of pupils?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the learner's healthy lifestyle and their academic performance?
9. How does the extent of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) implementation, including components such as hygiene education, water access, sanitation, deworming, and hygiene practices, influence the academic performance of students?
10. What are the unique practices of elementary schools relevant to the implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive evaluative research design is a methodological approach used in research to gather and analyze data to provide a detailed description of a phenomenon or event. It is a nonexperimental design that focuses on describing and understanding the experiences and perspectives of participants (Doyle et al., 2020).

In this study, the extent of implementation of the comprehensive WASH Program in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Laguna was collected from the health coordinators. The data were assessed using a survey method and data collected were analyzed and quantitatively interpreted using descriptive evaluative research design to provide a detailed description of the program.

To determine the healthy lifestyle attitudes of learners toward the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Schools (WinS) program, a descriptive survey research design was also employed. It allowed the researcher to gather information about learners' perceptions, experiences, and practices related to WinS without manipulating any variables. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire designed to measure learners' attitudes regarding water, sanitation, hygiene practices, and participation in WinS activities.

Sampling Technique

The study employed a cluster sampling technique in selecting the respondents, wherein each school was treated as a distinct cluster. The researcher specifically selected the central schools within Cluster 1, considering that these schools have relatively higher allocations from the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), which enable them to better support and sustain the implementation of the WASH (Water, Sanitation,

and Hygiene) program. Cluster 1 consisted of eight (8) schools located in the municipalities of Siniloan, Santa Maria, Pakil, Paete, Mabitac, Lumban, Kalayaan, and Pagsanjan. From these clusters, intermediate-level teachers and pupils were randomly selected as respondents. A total of 170 teachers and 367 pupils participated in the study. In addition, eight (8) School Health Coordinators, representing each school in Cluster 1, were included in the study. This sampling technique was appropriate as it allowed efficient data gathering from naturally occurring groups while ensuring that participants were randomly selected within each cluster.

When using clustered sampling, the population is divided into clusters and then randomly select from each cluster. It is useful for large or geographically spread populations (Siti Asmah, 2025).

Research Instrument

The researcher developed two sets of questionnaires; the first set was devised from the monitoring tool on the Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd (OKD) program implementation, which includes WASH in Schools, while the other set was specifically designed based on the variables and structure outlined in the conceptual framework. The validity and reliability of the questionnaires depended on their passing the evaluation of experts. A pilot testing of the study was also conducted.

The questionnaire for the principal, school health coordinator, and teachers was divided into three parts. It included the profile of the respondents, the school profile, the extent of the WinS program, and a survey on their unique practices in their school. The first part covered the personal profile of the respondents, which included the name (optional), age, gender, position, and length of coordinatorship of the health coordinator. The second part covered the school profile, containing the name of the school, position of the school head, school type, and total number of enrollments.

The third part covered the extent of implementation of the comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program. It contained components such as water access, sanitation, hygiene, deworming, and hygiene education. The last part focused on their unique practices in relation to the WinS program.

The other set of questionnaires was intended for the learners, which included the status of academic performance of the learners, learners' healthy lifestyle, preventive health services and responsibility for their own health, learners' attitudes, norms, and behavior, and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene program. These components were evaluated using the

Likert's Scale given below.

Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High Extent (<i>The statement is 81-100% true</i>)
3.50-4.49	Agree/High Extent (<i>The statement is 61-80% true</i>)

2.50-3.49	Neutral /Moderate Extent(<i>The statement is 41-60% true</i>)
1.50-2.49	Disagree/Low Extent (<i>The statement is 21-40% true</i>)
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree/Very Low Extent (<i>The statement is 0-20% true</i>)

To ensure the reliability and effectiveness of the research instrument, validation of self-made questionnaire was conducted through rigorous pilot testing with a representative sample of participants.

Cronbach's results are as follows:

Variance.S (Questions)	Variance.S (Respondents)	Alpha
167.24	23.163	0.8868365

Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher prepared the necessary documents for approval and then scheduled the submission and checking of the pertinent documents needed to conduct the study. Proper coordination with district supervisors, school heads, and teachers was ensured to facilitate the distribution and retrieval of the data needed.

This study used cluster sampling techniques to randomly select the respondents. The privacy of the respondents and the confidentiality of their answers were also secured during the conduct of the study.

To arrive at the most significant answers and substantial analysis, the following statistical tools and treatments were used. For the extent of implementation of the comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene programs in public elementary schools in terms of water access, sanitation, hygiene, deworming, and hygiene education, weighted mean and rank were used.

Correlation was used to test relationships between quantitative variables or categorical variables. In other words, it was a measure of how things were related. In this study, the significant relationship between learners' attitudes, norms, and behaviors and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene program in public elementary schools was tested. The significant relationship between learners' healthy lifestyle, preventive health services, and responsibility for their own health and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene program in public elementary schools was also examined. Furthermore, the significant relationship between the extent of attitudes, norms, behavioral intentions and the academic performance of pupils, as well as the significant relationship between the extent of sanitation practices of pupils and their academic performance, were tested.

Lastly, the significant relationship between the extent of WASH implementation including hygiene education, water access, sanitation, deworming, and hygiene practices and the academic performance of students was also determined.

RESULTS

Table 1. Extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program.

Extent of Implementation of Wins Program	School Heads		Students		Teachers		Overall WM	Overall Verbal Interpretation
	AWM	VI	AWM	VI	AWM	VI		
Water Access	4.56	VHE	4.40	HE	4.45	HE	4.47	High Extent
Sanitation	4.40	HE	4.39	HE	4.16	HE	4.31	High Extent
Hygiene	3.89	HE	4.28	HE	4.26	HE	4.15	High Extent
Deworming	4.69	VHE	4.59	VHE	4.11	HE	4.46	High Extent
Hygiene Education	4.03	HE	4.47	HE	4.53	VHE	4.34	High Extent

Table 2. Extent of sanitation of pupils into learning healthy lifestyle, preventive health services, and responsibility for their own health and extent of sanitation of pupils as to attitude, norms and behavior.

Extent of Sanitation of Pupils	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Learners Healthy Lifestyle, Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for Own Health	4.577	Very High Extent
Attitude, Norms and Behavior	4.694	Very High Extent

Table 3. Status of Academic Performance of Pupils

	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Status of Academic Performance of Pupils	4.553	Very High Extent

Table 4. Relationship between learners’ attitude, norms and behaviors and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene program.

	Statistical Treatment	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Relationship between the learners’attitude, norms and behaviors and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene program.	Spearman’s Correlation	0.596	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 5. Relationship between the Learners’ Healthy Lifestyle Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for own health and the extent of implementation of comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene program.

	Statistical Treatment	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Relationship between Learners Healthy Lifestyle, Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for Own Health and the Extent of Implementation of Comprehensive Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Program	Spearman’s Correlation	0.603	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 6. Relationship between the extent of attitude, norms, and behavioral intentions on academic performance of pupils.

	Statistical Treatment	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Relationship between the extent of attitude, norms, and behavioral intentions on academic performance of pupils.	Spearman's Correlation	0.556	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 7. Relationship between the learner's healthy lifestyle and their academic performance

	Statistical Treatment	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Relationship between the learners' healthy lifestyle and their academic performance	Spearman's Correlation	0.548	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 8. Influence of Academic Performance to the extent of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) implementation, including components such as hygiene education, water access, sanitation, deworming, and hygiene practices.

Model Coefficients - Academic Performance						
Predictor	Estimate	SE	T	p	Decision	Interpretation
Intercept	0.472	0.2728	1.73	0.084		
Learners Healthy Lifestyle Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for Own Health	0.322	0.0807	3.98	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Learners Attitude, Norms, and Behavior	0.556	0.0777	7.15	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Model Fit Measures	R	R ²				

1 Model Coefficients - Extent of Implementation of WASH						
Predictor	Estimate	SE	T	p	Decision	Interpretation
Intercept	0.47	0.2628	1.79	0.075		
Learners Healthy Lifestyle Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for Own Health	0.421	0.0778	5.42	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Learners Attitude, Norms, and Behavior	0.43	0.0749	5.75	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Model Fit Measures						
Model 1	R	R ²				
1	0.62	0.384				
Model Coefficients - Academic Performance						
Predictor	Estimate	SE	T	p	Decision	Interpretation
Intercept	2.613	0.2192	11.92	<.001		
Extent of Implementation of WASH	0.439	0.0493	8.9	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Model Fit Measures					Reject Ho	Significant
Model 1	R	R ²				
1	0.422	0.178				

Table 9. Unique practices of elementary schools relevant to the implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program.

Sample Responses	Codes	Themes	Interpretation
Group handwashing, toothbrushing, daily hygiene routines	Daily routines, supervised hygiene	Structured Hygiene Practices	Schools institutionalize regular hygiene activities to develop consistent sanitation habits.

Sample Responses	Codes	Themes	Interpretation
Adequate toilets, handwashing stations, safe drinking water	Facilities, access	Provision of WINS Facilities	Functional facilities support effective hygiene implementation.
Integrating hygiene in Science, GMRC, TLE, MAPEH	Curriculum integration	Integration Hygiene Curriculum	of Hygiene concepts are in embedded in lessons to reinforce learning.
Cleaning schedules, waste segregation, drainage maintenance	Waste management, sanitation	Sanitation Waste Management	and Regular cleaning ensures a safe and healthy environment.
Teachers monitor hygiene kits, reminders, supervision	Teacher monitoring	Teacher Supervision Monitoring	Teachers ensure and compliance with hygiene practices.
WINS team, monitoring and evaluation	Program management	Program Management Sustainability	Schools establish and systems for continuous implementation.
Activities for parents, stakeholders, campaigns	Collaboration	Stakeholder Participation	Partnerships strengthen program sustainability.
Student-led cleanliness, hygiene monitors, SELG/YES-O involvement	Student leadership	Learner Participation Leadership	Learners actively and promote hygiene practices among peers.
Hygiene buddy system, peer education, advocacy	Peer mentoring	Peer Support and Advocacy	Students influence each other to sustain hygiene practices.
Waste-to-resource programs, incentives	eco-Recycling initiatives	Innovative Waste Management Practices	Schools introduce creative approaches to waste segregation.
Gender-sensitive toilets, menstrual hygiene support	Inclusive facilities	Gender-Responsive and Inclusive Practices	Schools ensure equitable and access to hygiene facilities.
Posters, signage, campaigns, global handwashing activities	Awareness programs	Hygiene Promotion and Advocacy	Visual and campaign strategies strengthen awareness.

DISCUSSION

Extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program.

The findings in Table 1 emphasized that the WASH program was highly implemented across all components. However, continuous improvements were still needed in infrastructure, resource provision, stakeholder participation, and learner involvement to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the program.

In the study of Dominic (2026) among the core elements of the WINS program, sanitation was highly prioritized and most consistently applied. School facilities and basic cleanliness are essential for preventing disease and ensuring a safe learning environment.

Extent of sanitation of pupils into learning healthy lifestyle, preventive health services, and responsibility for their own health and extent of sanitation of pupils as to attitude, norms and behavior.

Table 2 evaluated the extent of sanitation practices among pupils in terms of healthy lifestyle, preventive health services, and responsibility for their own health. The overall results indicated a very high extent, showing that learners demonstrated strong awareness and consistent practices related to personal health. These findings reveal that students consistently display established self-care habits while prioritizing cleanliness and health. Contrary to this finding, Nurlina et al., (2026) observed that many students had limited knowledge of correct handwashing procedures which suggests a critical need for initiative programs to promote handwashing with soap, personal and environmental hygiene, appropriate waste disposal, and the consumption of nutritious food.

In terms of attitudes, norms, and behavioral intentions. The overall results indicated a “Very High Extent”, showing that learners possessed very positive attitudes toward hygiene, although some perceived sanitation practices as time-consuming and demanding of effort. This suggests that despite the presence of awareness, improvements in students’ sanitation attitudes and motivation need to be strengthened to make hygiene a regular and effortless part of their daily routine. This is supported by a study by Win (2025), which found that students’ actual hygiene practices were inconsistent, particularly in schools with inadequate infrastructure, despite their sufficient hygiene knowledge and positive attitudes. The researcher suggested the use of behavioral cues, such as strategically placed posters, to reinforce hygiene habits and serve as constant reminders that encourage students to follow correct hygiene practices to strengthen hygiene education and support sustainable behavior change among school children.

Status of Academic Performance of Pupils

Table 3 presented the level of academic performance of pupils in school. The overall results indicated a “Very High Extent”, suggesting that hygiene and WASH conditions positively influenced students’ learning.

This finding aligns with the work of Armilla et al. (2025), who highlighted the significant relationship between Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) and the support of effective learning and overall school development. The study shows the effect of insufficient WASH facilities in Cebu City public junior high schools such as increase in cases of illness, decrease in school attendance, and poor academic performance. Poor WASH conditions also negatively impacted students’ physical comfort, mental well-being and classroom focus. Thus, strengthening and sustaining WASH programs with hygiene education integration were recommended to the Department of Education and local government units.

Relationship between learners’ attitude, norms and behaviors and the extent of implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene program.

The results show that all variables had a significant relationship, implying that improved WASH implementation led to more positive learner behaviors and attitudes. It further suggests that a consistent supply of adequate water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities would significantly improve students’ hygiene practices. Lawal et al., (2025) emphasized that the success of school WASH programs depends more on students’ practices which are shaped by social norms, cultural influences, and school-related factors rather than on infrastructure alone.

Relationship between the Learners’ Healthy Lifestyle Preventive Health Services and Responsibility for own health and the extent of implementation of comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene program.

The data in Table 5 reveals the significant relationship between learners’ healthy lifestyle, preventive health services, and responsibility for their own health, alongside the implementation of the comprehensive Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program. All correlations were statistically significant, indicating a meaningful relationship among the variables. It further implies that effective WASH implementation encouraged learners to practice proper hygiene and develop a stronger sense of responsibility for their own health. Farzali (2026) explained that integrated personal health education programs helped reduce the spread of infectious diseases in schools while also increasing students’ awareness and encouraging healthier lifestyles.

Relationship between the extent of attitude, norms, and behavioral intentions on academic performance of pupils.

Table 6 reveals a significant relationship between the extent of the respondents’ attitudes, norms and behavioral intentions and academic performance. The data suggests that pupils who demonstrate favorable attitudes toward hygiene, adhere to positive social

norms, and exhibit strong behavioral intentions tend to perform better academically. Learners who develop a positive attitude toward hygiene practices, such as regular handwashing, proper toilet use, and personal cleanliness, are more likely to maintain good health. A healthy pupil experiences fewer illnesses, which reduces absenteeism and ensures continuous participation in classroom activities. Sharma et al., (2024) emphasized that learners in schools with adequate WASH infrastructure are more likely to perform well academically compared to those in schools with unimproved facilities, even after accounting for psychosocial factors such as attitudes, norms, self-efficacy, and intentions.

Relationship between the learner's healthy lifestyle and their academic performance.

Table 7 illustrates a significant relationship between the learners' healthy lifestyle and their academic performance, suggesting that better health practices were associated with better academic outcomes. Consistent adherence to healthy routines promotes discipline, accountability, and hygiene awareness among pupils, fostering a learning environment that supports concentration and engagement. Thus, enhanced behavior positively affects both health outcomes and academic performance.

Zhang et al., (2025) found that good hygiene habits are crucial for students' physical health and support their cognitive and academic growth. They explain that regular hygiene routines improve students' abilities in self-management, self-care, and self-learning.

Influence of Academic Performance to the extent of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) implementation, including components such as hygiene education, water access, sanitation, deworming, and hygiene practices.

Table 8 presents the influence of academic performance on the extent of WASH implementation, including components such as hygiene education, water access, sanitation, deworming, and hygiene practices. The model explains a substantial portion of at variance in academic performance, indicating that academic performance influenced the extent of WASH implementation.

Unique practices of elementary schools relevant to the implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation, and hygiene program.

The data in Table 9 summarize the collected responses of teachers regarding the unique practices of elementary schools relevant to WASH implementation, highlighting the schools' innovative practices. The respondents further highlighted the active roles of teachers, students, and external stakeholders in supervising hygiene activities and ensuring the availability of necessary supplies. Teachers integrate proper hygiene education into subjects like Science and MAPEH, while also monitoring students' hygiene kits and daily practices. Student leaders act as hygiene monitors or join groups like SELG to lead cleanliness campaigns. Some schools also utilize "hygiene buddies" and eco-incentive programs, where students exchange recyclables for food or school supplies,

while stakeholders support school clean-up and maintenance efforts. Overall, the WINS program succeeds through the combination of classroom learning, student-led activities, and stakeholder engagement to create a safe and healthy environment for children to learn.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that a consistent supply of adequate water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities significantly improves students' hygiene practices. The implementation of the WinS Program encourages learners to practice proper hygiene and develop a stronger sense of responsibility for their health. Furthermore, adherence to school rules regarding cleanliness and cooperation fosters a supportive learning environment that enhances students' focus and engagement. Proper health habits that promote discipline also contribute to a better learning environment. In addition, the good condition of WinS infrastructure positively influences learners' academic achievement. The study further reveals that the success of WASH programs depends not only on the availability of facilities but also on learners' attitudes, norms, behaviors, healthy lifestyles, preventive health services, and personal health responsibility.

Based on these conclusions, it is recommended that WASH programs be expanded across other districts to further improve student health and learning outcomes. Hygiene education should continue to be integrated into daily classroom lessons and school activities to reinforce positive habits among learners. Parents and guardians should actively support hygiene campaigns to strengthen children's hygiene practices both at school and at home. Collaboration with the Local Government Unit (LGU) and other external stakeholders should also be strengthened to enhance the implementation and sustainability of the WinS Program. Lastly, future research should explore additional variables and conduct broader studies on the WinS Program to gain a more comprehensive understanding of its impact.

Recommendations

1. WASH programs should be expanded across other districts to further enhance student health and learning.
2. Hygiene education must continuously be integrated into daily classroom lessons and school activities.
3. Hygiene campaigns should be actively supported by parents and guardians, particularly to reinforce children's hygiene habits both in school and at home.
4. Collaboration with the Local Government Unit (LGU) and other external stakeholders should be strengthened to further support and enhance the WINS program.
5. Future research should examine additional variables and conduct a broader study on Wins Program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers secured informed consent from all participants and ensured that they had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point. Participants' anonymity and confidentiality were strictly protected throughout the research process. The study followed ethical standards by avoiding plagiarism, minimizing bias, and declaring no conflicts of interest. Furthermore, the findings of the study were used solely for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

This research would not have been possible without the guidance, support, and assistance of several individuals who contributed to the successful completion of this study. The researcher sincerely expresses heartfelt appreciation and gratitude to everyone who became part of this undertaking. First and foremost, the researcher gives thanks to the Almighty God for providing wisdom, strength, self-confidence, spiritual guidance, and countless blessings that made this study achievable. The researcher also extends sincere gratitude to the University President, Campus Director, Dean of the College of Teacher Education, research adviser, members of the panel, and especially to the respondents who willingly shared their time and valuable information necessary for the completion of this study.

REFERENCES

- Armilla M., Dinopol P., Jomud B., Kapuno J., Pesalbon S., Rentigrado C., and Reyes J. (2025) Students' and Teachers' Perception of Psychosocial Stress and Distraction from Poor Wash Conditions in Cebu City Public Schools., *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation* pp 354-392
- Chirgwin, H., Cairncross, S., Zehra, D., & Sharma Waddington, H. (2021). Interventions promoting uptake of water, sanitation and hygiene (wash) technologies in low-and middle-income countries: an evidence and gap map of effectiveness studies. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 17(4), e1194.
- Dominic, Hermano (2026) School Health Intervention: Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools (WinS) Program in Public Schools of the National Capital Region, Philippines, *Int. J. School. Health*. 2026; 13(1)
- Doyle, Louise, Catherine, McCabe., Brian, Keogh., Anne-Marie, Brady., Margaret, McCann. (2020). An overview of the qualitative descriptive design within nursing research. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(5):443-455. doi: 10.1177/1744987119880234
- Farzali S. (2026) Investigating the Quality and Improvement of Community Health as a Result of Personal Health Education. Vol. 47 No. 01 (2026)
- Lawal N., Aliyu D. G., Ibrahim H. M., Shehu A. A., and Barki K. (2025) Enhancing Water Sanitation and Hygiene Standards in Secondary Schools of Developing Countries: a Review and Conceptual Framework p.119 *FUDMA Journal of Sciences (FJS)* Vol. 9 No. 12, December, 2025, pp 178 – 187 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2025-0912-4254>
- McMichael, C., 2019. Water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) in schools in low-income countries: a review of evidence of impact. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Publ. Health* 16 (3), 359. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16030359>

- Nurlina M., Aslinda A., Harmawati H., Mohamad Nor N., Binti Zulkifli N., Mahmud R., and Halim A. (2026) Promoting Clean and Healthy Living in Schools: A Pre-Experimental Study on Disease Prevention. Vol. 9 No. 3 (2026): March 2026.
<https://doi.org/10.56338/mppki.v9i3.9064>
- Sharma, M. K., Adhikari, R., van Tejligen, E., Devkota, B., & Khanal, S. P. (2024). Improved water, Sanitation and Hygiene Facilities at School and their effect on educational achievement in basic level students in Nepal. *International Journal of Health Promotion and Education*, 1-12.
- Tsekleves, E., Fonseca Braga, M., Abonge, C., Santana, M., Pickup, R., Yongabi Anchang, K., ... & Roy, M. (2022). Community engagement in water, sanitation and hygiene in sub-Saharan Africa: does it WASH?. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 12(2), 143-156.
- United Nations Children's Fund. (2020). *The Importance of Sanitation for All, Especially Children*.
- World Health Organization & United Nations Children's Fund. (2025). *Joint monitoring programme: Progress on drinking water, sanitation and hygiene in schools*.
<https://washdata.org>
- Win, C. Z., Jawjit, W., Thongdara, R., Gheewala, S. H., & Prapasongsa, T. (2024). Towards more sustainable water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) projects in magway region, Myanmar. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 26(9), 22149-22173.
- Yusuf, M., 2020. Kenyan union says COVID-19 in schools putting teachers at risk. Published on VOA news on 2 November 2020. Available at. <https://www.voanews.com/africa/kenyan-union-says-covid-19-schools-putting-teachers-risk>, 2020. accessed on 17.11.2020.
- Zhang, Z., Wang, L. & Qu, Y. The interplay between positive lifestyle habits and academic excellence in higher education. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 12, 337 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-04630-4>